

INFLUENCE OF INFORMATIONAL STRESS ON STUDENTS' STUDY ACTIVITY

Ergashev Hasanboy

Independent researcher of Public Security
University of the Republic of Uzbekistan
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10434089>

Abstract. The article shows the psychological factors of informational stress in cadets. In particular, the issue of the manifestation of informational stress on their educational activities was analyzed. Also, the issue of the relationship between informational stress and educational activities in cadets was examined based on empirical research.

Keywords. Stress, resilience to stress, informational stress, academic performance, resilience to stress, extrovert, introvert, locus of control, personal behavior.

Аннотация. Мақолада курсантларда информацион стресснинг юзага келишининг психологик омилларини кўрсатиб ўтилган. Айниқса, информацион стресснинг намоён бўлишини уларнинг ўқув фаолиятига таъсири масаласи таҳлил қилинган. Шунингдек, курсантларда юзага келадиган информацион стресснинг ўқув фаолияти билан алоқадорлиги масаласи эмпирик тадқиқотлар асосида текширилган.

Калит сўзлар. стресс, стрессга барқарорлик, информацион стресс, ўқув фаолияти, стрессга барқарорлик, экстраверт, интроверт, локус назорати, шахсий хулқ-атвор.

Абстрактный. В статье показаны психологические факторы информационного стресса у курсантов. В частности, был проанализирован вопрос проявления информационного напряжения в их учебной деятельности. Также на основе эмпирического исследования рассмотрен вопрос о связи информационного стресса и учебной деятельности курсантов.

Ключевые слова. стресс, стрессоустойчивость, информационный стресс, успеваемость, стрессоустойчивость, экстраверт, интроверт, локус контроля, личностное поведение.

Informational stress is caused by an overwhelming flow of information, a lack of time to absorb it, or a lack of personal cognitive capabilities of an individual.

In a broader sense, informational stress is when the subject exerts too much effort to complete the task assigned to him in the process of performing a certain activity, imposes loads to the extent that he cannot afford it, feels a high

sense of responsibility in this process, and is squeezed without being able to make the right decision in solving and resolving the situations that arise. also occurs in the situation of excessive tension that occurs for the psyche [1].

Let's consider the factors underlying the occurrence of informational stress. One of the most important aspects of the modern lifestyle is the presence of excessive information, which destroys the psychological ecology of a person and leads to informational pollution of his life. These include not only the reception of information that is actively encountered in connection with the narrow scope and professional activities of a person, but also the information distributed through mass media that are generally accepted and used.

Most of the research on informational stress has been conducted in connection with those working in the field of computer technology. And in all of them, the personal behavioral reaction of the individual in extreme situations was also considered [1].

According to the results of many researches, if a person is forced to accept and work with information in a very fast and responsible manner, that person develops an informational neurosis. In this case, the accountability factor reflects a state of mobilization or mental stress related to the value of information and focus on avoiding mistakes. Taking into account that this state is conditioned by the situation, it can be said that it can be passed without mental stress.

According to N.M. Sandomirskiy, until recently we have been thinking about the impact of informational stress on the brain of an adult, now there is information that informational stress begins to haunt the human brain from the moment a child acquires speech [2].

Informational stress depends on the subject's self-assessment of the danger of stress during an extreme signal or situation. It should be noted that not only the real stressful situation itself, but also its imagination is perceived as a threat, and this also causes informational stress.

According to many researches, a specific reaction in a stressful situation is related not only to stimulation, but also to the mental characteristics of the subject. Individual psychological differences have been studied, which are clearly manifested in the individual's response and behavior to the same stressor. Emphasis is placed on the fact that the emotional reaction of a person is an internal condition that determines his mental activity. It is for this reason that the role of the individual's personal response to external influences in the formation and development of the stress reaction is important [4].

A person responds to external influences through the structure of his psyche, especially his emotionality.

It is established that the role of strict typological characteristics of the individual in the reaction to extreme influences is significant. It is known that emotionally reactive individuals are characterized by a significant change in their psyche under extreme conditions of activity. In extroverts, as a result of stress, inhibition processes develop faster than introverts and normalize more slowly.

J. Rotter paid attention to the fact that people perceive stress differently in external and internal locus of control.

The problems of learning how a person behaves and mentally controls himself in extreme conditions of activity are carried out in several directions. In general, the determination of the main characteristics and types of several individuals, their actions in such a situation, the impact of extreme situations on the personal status, in the adaptation processes, is dedicated to this or that personal characteristic society. But there are no separate works dedicated to the place of personal description in the regulation of the emergence and development process of informational stress [3].

Informational stress is caused by an overwhelming flow of information, a lack of time to absorb it, or a person's lack of cognitive abilities. In the recent years, the abundance of diverse information flows entering the lives of all active people, especially the cadets who are among the most active members of society, as well as the lack of time to master them, cause some problems. In particular, such an intense flow of information coming to cadets is definitely one of the factors that cause informational stress in them. This situation, if not prevented, can lead to the formation of a problem called information neurosis. According to the results of many researches, it can be said that the high sense of responsibility in receiving information and the emotional feeling of its volume lead to informational tension and this can also increase informational stress and ultimately informational neurosis. At this point, if we pay attention to the stress that occurs mainly in the educational process, the informational stress observed in the cadets has a negative effect on the students' desire to know about the educational activities, their interest in the world of sciences, and in some cases it can extinguish such interests and derail the educational process to some extent.

During educational activities and in any educational process, educational stress is combined with informational stress. The conflict that occurs as a result of informational stress consists of the following. There is an imbalance between

the large amount of information and the lack of time to absorb it. Then the cadet does not independently analyze this information. In other words, the cadet learns not to think independently. Does he memorize the text by mechanical repetition? If they don't directly accept what they see on TV and think about the next process without discussing it, they easily adopt the ready thought of others. All this leads to one result - the cadet's ability to think, that is, he cannot use the capabilities of his brain correctly and properly.

According to the data, the formation of informative perceptions about situations such as real and potential danger, damage, loss, difficulty is carried out with the help of cognitive processes. The assimilation of information in this way based on the interdependence of various mental processes leads to a selective attitude towards it, as a result of which information of a certain importance is selected. This, in turn, leads to the interruption of data in memory [1].

It is known that the increase in the flow of information, the lack of time and the limitation of opportunities for its assimilation are among the factors that cause informational stress in them. Therefore, studying the factors that cause informational stress in cadets and the degree of manifestation is one of the main tasks of our research work.

The methodology-questionnaire conducted in order to study the sensitivity to informational stress in cadets was conducted in the group of testers and the results were analyzed in terms of quantity and quality. The results of this quantitative analysis are shown in the table below.

Table 1

Table of informational stress indicators of testers

Testers	High	Medium	Low
1st course	34%	30,3%	23,5%
3rd course	32,4%	28,2%	24,5%

According to the results of the table, high sensitivity to informational stress was 32.4% and 34% of the test scores. This indicator shows that the test takers in both courses have a high susceptibility to stress. This situation may arise as a result of the large amount of information given to them during the educational process and their inability to allocate time correctly. The fact that most cadets do not have the ability to distinguish the necessary information from the useless when learning educational materials, as well as the lack of time

due to the accumulation of assignments without completing them on time during the educational process, there is a high probability of causing informational stress in any cadet.

A different result can be seen if the high scores of the examinees are analyzed by courses, that is, in the 1st courses, this indicator is 34% on average, and in the 3rd year it is equal to 32.4%. From these indicators, it can be concluded that the increase in knowledge, skills and experiences of a person led to a decrease in informational stress. The more the cadet participates in educational activities, the more comprehensive the process of adaptation to this process, together with the skills and competencies, takes place, which in itself will not affect the level of acceptance of the flow of information.

In these cadets with a high susceptibility to stress, it can be observed based on the results of the methodology that the basic method-constructive methods such as sleep, recreational activity, feeling of support in communication with others, as a factor of stress relief, are rarely used. These methods, as it is known, do not help to eliminate the stress situation in a person.

Among the examinees, the average score is 30.3% and 28.2%, and some differences between the courses are noticeable. According to this, they try to plan all their work on time in order not to get informational stress, but it is noted that the characteristic of willpower towards the goal is manifested in them depending on the situation of anxiety. But this indicates that the cadets' information flow, time management skills and qualifications are not fully developed.

The test subjects of this group showed that they mostly used constructive methods to overcome their stress. Even this situation can be enough reason for them to decrease this indicator.

The low level of exposure to informational stress was only 66%. Their stress susceptibility rate was 23.5% in the 1st year and 24.5% in the 3rd year. Based on the result of individual interview and observation with them, it can be said that the cadets have a different way of thinking and outlook on life. That is, educational activities are important for them, but there are more important tasks and goals in life that a person should strive for more.

The results of our research showed that in general, the level of informational stress was quite high among the students of both courses, and this was also reflected in their educational activities. Also, the main factor, as stated by Rissler, is evidenced by the acceptance of the external situation or situation by the individual, the quality of the demands of others that threaten his abilities

and opportunities. In this case, it will be possible to show cases where the cadets reflect subjectively, that is, they perceive the commanders as strict, as there are no resources for mastering the assigned tasks, or on the contrary, there are too many resources that are required to be mastered.

Used literature:

1. Бодров. В.А. Информацион стресс. Москва – 2000.
2. Изард К. Э. Психология эмоций. — СПб.: Питер, 1999.
3. Китаев-Смык Л. А. Психология стресса. — М.: Наука, 1983.
4. Селье Г. Стресс без дистресса. — Рига: Виеда, 1992.

